

Motivation

Sputtering technologies are widely used to study functional materials. In the case of hard magnetic materials, the interest is 2-fold. On the one hand, films can be used to fabricate micro-magnets for applications in micro-devices. On the other hand, they can be used to study and optimize the extrinsic magnetic properties of the material itself. Compositionally graded films are now being used for the high throughput analysis of the effect of chemical composition and thermal treatments on the magnetic properties of hard magnetic [1]. In all cases, film deposition at elevated temperatures and/or subsequent annealing can cause mechanical stress and deformation in the magnetic layer, as has been evidenced by the extrusion of a liquid secondary during annealing of NdFeB films [2]. Such mechanical stress may affect the lattice parameters and magnetic properties of the film, and may even lead to film fracture and/or delamination of thick films. Understanding and minimizing stress is important for both fundamental and applied studies.

Research

Layer sputtering route

Extrusion [2] and delamination problems

We use as a basis Townsend's theory for multilayer composition [3]

$$\sigma_i^k = f \left\{ \begin{array}{l} E_i(T); \nu_i(T); \alpha_i(T); \\ t_i; \sigma_{RE0}; \sigma_{u(i)}; T^k; \\ \text{material database} \end{array} \right\} \rightarrow \text{optimisation} \rightarrow \{t_r, t_b, \text{material}, T_{depr}\}$$

Unknown are $\sigma_{u(i)} = f(T, t_i, \text{material}) \Rightarrow$ from $\alpha_{REFeB}(T) = f(T, t_i, \text{composition}) \Rightarrow$ experiment [4]

Dependence of the relaxation Cu-layer thickness and stresses in the studied REFeB layer on the coefficient of thermal expansion of REFeB (particular case)

Stress distribution in a multilayer system with different thicknesses of buffer and relaxation layers ($\alpha_{REFeB} = 5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/K}$) $T_{ann} = 700^\circ \text{C}$

Conclusions

- The use of a combination of buffer, capping and relaxation layers is a possible technical solution to minimize the build up of stresses in magnetic (e.g., REFeB) films during sample preparation, to avoid lattice distortion or film delamination. During sample preparation, it is desirable to keep low compressive stresses (less than $\sim 10 \text{ MPa}$) in the REFeB-layer after its deposition and cooling and small tensile (of the order of $\sim 1 \text{ MPa}$) stresses during annealing.
- We recommend using materials with high coefficients of thermal elongation, high ductility and strength as the material of the relaxation layer. For example, a copper relaxation layer may be suitable for such an application.
- Depending on the thermal expansion coefficient of the magnetic layer and the thickness of the relaxant layer, it may be better to deposit the latter on the top or bottom side of the substrate. For the Si-Cu-Ta-REFeB-Ta system (0.5-0.0009-0.0001-0.001-0.0001 mm) at $\alpha_{REFeB} = 5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ 1/K}$ and 700°C annealing, the residual stress level in the REFeB layer is less than 2 MPa , which is 50 times smaller than the same multilayer but with the Cu layer.
- One of the challenges of the quantitative application of the proposed approach is to know the mechanical characteristics (elasticity, strength, elongations as a function of temperatures, thickness, specific conditions) in the magnetic layer at all stages of sample preparation.
- The impact of using relaxation layers in multilayer stacks containing magnetic layers will now be studied experimentally.

References

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ABSTRACT

Applying the theory of mechanical interaction of thin films in a composite system, we propose methods for controlling the formation of stresses in (Nd,La,Ce)FeB films. Tuning the level of stress in Ta buffer and capping layers may be an effective method to reduce stresses in the magnetic film. Another way to control stresses is to use a relaxation layer deposited on the substrate. In this case, materials with high plastic properties can be used for the relaxation layer, which can provide additional advantages. By adjusting the layer order, mechanical properties, thickness and temperature during deposition, it should be possible to achieve the desired stress level in certain cases. The choice of mechanical properties for stress control layers should be based on optimised calculations taking into account material databases, material properties and equipment limitations.

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